

THE DEMISE OF TECHNICAL SUBJECTS IN SOUTH AFRICA: A PERSPECTIVE FROM UNIVERSITY PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The integration of practical hands-on skills in technical subjects like mechanical, civil, and electrical technologies is critical for schools in a country desperate for technological emancipation. This is to produce skilled manpower for job creation and to help improve the economy which is battered due to technical skills gap. However, it looks like using the school's practical hands-on skills to address economic challenges and youth unemployment in South Africa is not yielding the required results considering the skyrocketing high unemployment rate. This paper aims to examine the dilemma of technical skills and explore strategies for revitalizing technical subject specializations. The study was limited to Civil Technology's Construction, Civil Services, and Woodworking specializations and was conducted on 79 pre-service technology education teachers from 4 higher education institutions offering technology education teacher training programs. Using mixed-methods research design, data was collected using questionnaires followed by semi-structured interviews to ascertain how learners were exposed to hands-on activities. Data collected through interviews were transcribed after each interview and typed, showing respondents' quotes. The data were then coded, analyzed, and discussed thematically. Quantitative data were presented and analyzed statistically to give a distribution in a table. The findings revealed, among others, inadequately qualified teaching personnel, tools, and equipment, obsolete tools and equipment, and a rather weak support system for technical subjects. The study calls for responsible Department of Basic Education offices and businesses to assist in the revitalization of technical subject specializations, as these are considered the solution to a country's unemployment burden.

KEYWORDS: civil technology, practical hands-on skills, technical subjects, youth unemployment

INTRODUCTION

In South African schools, the Civil Technology specialization is part of the technical education subjects taught in grades 10–12. The specialization encompasses plumbing, construction, and woodwork. According to the Department of Basic Education (DBE, 2014), the specialization is subdivided into construction, civil services, and woodworking to embrace practical skills. By design, these specializations are practical in nature, requiring a practical approach to teaching pedagogies. Makgato (2011) argues that technology education, formerly known as technical education, has been conceived as being associated with the acquisition of motor skills. For example, in the construction area, learners are introduced to concrete and brick structures. In Civil Services, learners are exposed to the supply of cold and hot water supplies to buildings, sewerage systems, and storm water, while they are introduced to roof trusses and any part of a building made of timber in the woodworking area.

In essence, the specializations mirror technical education in the sense that hands-on skills are still central. In schools, learners are required to choose one specialization from Grade 10 to Grade 12, where they are expected to develop technical hands-on skills through the manipulation of tools, machinery, and materials infused in the Practical Assessment Tasks (PATs). According to the Curriculum Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS), schools offering civil technology specializations must have well-equipped workshops for learners to complete the PATs (DBE, 2014). The PATs account for 25% of the learner's final mark (DBE, 2014).

Through the integrated completion of theoretical work and practical tasks, Civil Technology Grade 12 graduates could enter apprenticeships to prepare them for a trade test (DBE, 2014). Therefore, it's very critical for teaching pedagogies to be practical. However, that requires strong instructional practice that embraces theory and practice where teachers understand their roles for technical skill development (Blayi et al., 2022). However, that looks like a fallacy because theory is preferred. For example, Maeko & Makgato (2017) discovered that technical subjects in schools have shifted from hands-on skills acquisition to theory for most of the available time because of lacking tools, materials and equipment. In the study, teachers revealed that the government does not supply schools with materials and equipment but shockingly emphasizes the importance of practical, hands-on skills when addressing the media.

If implemented correctly, the specializations offer the potential to equip learners with technical skills aligned to the world of work. For example, Maeko & Makgato (2014) found that some of the learners who went through technical schools in the olden days were either self-employed or employed without any further training. That was significant to allow learners flexibility, which does not seem to be the case now where technical matric graduates are also queuing for employment. In general, the high unemployment rate in South Africa has led to calls for vocational education to lean towards entrepreneurship. This necessitated a major curriculum shift for the Department of Basic Education (DBE) to invest more in the country's technical high schools. It is assumed that this will create a learner's path in education linked to employment and self-reliance. Despite such interventions, learners are still exiting the system without the much-needed skills, relegating them to the unemployment ladder.

PURPOSE FOR THE STUDY

The study investigated the demise of technical subjects with reference to the development of technical hands-on skills in South Africa. The focus was on pre-service teachers who have been to schools for Work Integrated Learning (WIL) teaching the Civil Technology specializations from Grades 10–12. These are teachers who, upon completion of their studies, will be employed to impart technical, hands-on skills to school learners for flexibility in entrepreneurship and academic routes. In schools, technical skills development has been observed to be a far-fetched theory owing to a lack of resources. This unfortunate trend placed learners in a very difficult situation as they were unable to fend for themselves after their Grade 12 schooling years. This unfortunate situation could be that learners have limited or non-exposure to practical hands-on skills, which could be linked to an unprecedented skyrocketing rate of unemployment amongst the youth.

Essentially, this study seeks to contribute to the critical discourse surrounding technical skills development in schools aimed at creating opportunities when learners graduate from Grade 12. I am of the view that, with proper implementation, the vocational nature of civil technology specializations has the potential to prepare learners to earn a living immediately after the schooling years. This study pertains to the demise of technical subjects in South Africa within the education domain. Investigating this research question is crucial in order to elucidate the research findings that are pertinent to the specific inquiries below:

1. What is the state of technical subjects in South African schools?
2. What are the challenges facing schools in their teaching and learning of technical subjects?

LITERATURE REVIEW

THE PARADOX IN CIVIL TECHNOLOGY SPECIALIZATIONS

Civil technology specializations can produce quality entrepreneurs and job creators if handled carefully. The practical nature of the specialization topics is well aligned to the technical, hands-on skills pathway aligned to the world of work. However, it looks like such a thing remains a pipedream, as the schooling system is still failing in many other respects. This paper was conducted on the 3rd year Civil Technology pre-service students' teachers to get information on the status of the subjects in schools where students' teachers went for Work Integrated Learning (WIL) as part of their training requirements.

Magolego et al., (2023) attest that some teachers focus on the theoretical part of the subjects because they lack skills to facilitate practical lessons. Being a vast area that it is, civil technology exposes learners to skills in cabinet making, building inspector, quantity surveying, architect, draftsman, building surveying, engineering technician (civil), engineering technologist (civil), and civil engineer, amongst others, through the PATs. Moreover, if learners don't want to proceed with the academic route to further their studies at universities, they should be able to opt for apprenticeships to become artisans or entrepreneurs. The above is indicative of the vast technical skills career pathway provided by the specializations.

To expose learners to skills, schools are therefore expected to possess materials, equipment, and other consumables as mentioned. For example, in the construction specialization, basic tools and equipment such as a square shove, spade, wheelbarrow, metal pegs, brick trowel, and spirit level,

to mention but a few, are critical. The woodworking specialization requires tools such as wooden mallets, try squares, marking gauges, and tenon saws, for example. Lastly, the Civil Services would need a pipe vice, hacksaw, pipe cutters (copper tubes), and a shifting spanner for learners to manipulate. These are some of the few basic tools that the specializations need to complete the PATs for hands-on skills. Nevertheless, it does not help schools to possess equipment and tools while teachers are unable to utilize them in the teaching of the subjects.

TECHNICAL SCHOOLS: A KEY FACTOR FOR HANDS-ON SKILLS DEVELOPMENT

As articulated by Mtshali & Ramaligela (2020), technical schools are training sectors developed to address the shortage of technical skills. As such, the school curriculum for civil technology shows that ideally, learners graduating from Grade 12 should already possess the practical skills needed to enter apprenticeships without further training (DBE, 2014). From Sweden perspective, apprenticeships entail a motive where hands-on skills are developed through working with materials (Andersson et al., 2015).

In South Africa, the apprenticeship learning program is seen as one way of training the unemployed and enabling them to obtain a qualification to work as artisans (Department of Labour, 2013). Therefore, civil technology learners should be equipped with a unique skill, placing them apart from other learners and in categories desired by industry. From this discussion, civil technology teaching pedagogies should be rooted in the practical aspects of the subject. As such, it is expected that learners should be spending time manipulating tools and equipment, which is regarded as learning by doing. In this regard, Adjrah (2014) claim that to satisfy the practical goals of all technical subjects, like civil technology specializations in Togo, there is a need for time and resources.

To prepare learners for economic survival, it is contended that technical schools have the capacity to develop manual skills and transfer practical hands-on skills for this purpose (Maeko, 2020). As articulated by Makgato (2011), all learners graduating from any civil technology specialization in South African high schools are expected to possess economically important skills suitable for sustenance or employment after the schooling period. This expectation of practical hands-on skills can only be realistic if essential practical equipment, such as machinery and hand tools, is provided for learners. This shows how viable technical schools should be economically.

THE PRACTICAL ASPECT IN CIVIL TECHNOLOGY SPECIALIZATIONS

It is worth mentioning that in 2023, the PAT for Construction required learners to build a one and a half-brick pier using lime and sand. The task would expose learners to the use of spades, shovels, and other tools mentioned together with the casting of concrete and the use of formwork. The Woodworking PAT required learners to manufacture a wooden chair with backrest support with the potential to expose learners to marking, cutting, and applying appropriate joints; and lastly, the Civil Services PAT required learners to engage with tools such as pipe vices and plumb bobs, for example, to set the gradient of the sewage pipe.

The PATs promote the integration of theory and practice, which is the key aim of the subject of civil technology (Mokhothu, 2020). Though the PATs, the use of projects like moldings, simple construction of wood joints, casting of concrete foundation, laying of blocks or bricks, floor tiling,

etc. becomes necessary with the purpose of providing an opportunity for hands-on practical in Zimbabwe (Chakamba et al., 2013). These are real life cutting edge technical skills requiring time for learners to start a career as trades people. According to Nani (2014), teaching practical subjects in schools needs more time to produce individuals who can create jobs for themselves.

So, to do justice, the teaching of practical subjects in civil technology specializations with so much practical underpinning cannot be given the same teaching time as mathematics and English, for example. In a study that was conducted in Zimbabwe, Chakamba et al. (2013) contest that since the specializations are practically oriented, less theory should be taught. Within that context, it is presumed that because practical needs time, learners should be given more time to engage in practical hands-on skills. In this case, Bhebhe & Maila (2016) vows learners will have time to get exposure to real world technical hands-on skills enabling them to establish their own businesses as entrepreneurs. However, Maeko (2020) argued that the teaching of practically oriented subjects in South African schools is generally hindered by several factors, including lack of time, equipment, materials, and teacher incompetencies. Maeko (2020) further points out that this then brings a disadvantage to learners who do not become familiar with using the equipment.

Similarly, these challenges may be compounded by other reasons, ranging from infrastructural issues in the educational system (Blayi et al., 2022).

CURRENT CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

The development of technical skills in South Africa remains key to offer learners skills for real world of work. However, such requires time, tools, equipment, and other consumables for learners to interact with. As articulated by Kwami & Manabete (2022), this would effectively develop manual labor skills, which are in high demand in sub-Saharan countries. In line with the above, the DBE (2014) posits that teachers must infuse activities to promote practical skills development, preparing learners for artisanship, amongst other things. In a study conducted in Japan, evidence suggest that technical skills provide better labor market outcomes (Ogawa, 2023).

Nevertheless, Maeko (2020) notes that such training remains a dream, as hands-on skills training in schools offering civil technology specializations is not functional in South Africa. For example, Maeko (2020) postulates that PATs are not given enough time even on schools' timetables, let alone lacking proper workshops, but focus more on theoretical concepts. This study therefore sought pre-service teachers' perceptions to understand the state of technical skills development in a country where, according to Statistics South Africa, the high unemployment rate is sitting at 63.9% for those aged 15–24 and 42.1% for those aged 25–34 years (Stats SA, 2023).

It is contended that the quality of skills training offered by technical education subjects has been signaled as falling short of the required levels with little alignment to the needs of the labor market (Msibi, 2021). Msibi further notes that the failure of the education system to produce the technical skills required for the country's technological change constrains its ability to grow and generate more employment. Bhebhe & Maila (2016) contend that the upsetting unemployment situation in developing countries like South Africa is compelling curriculum planners to investigate new educational reforms that will allow learners to gain technical, hands-on skills for their employability. But, in their wisdom, the DBE introduced technical mathematics and technical sciences to partner technical subjects. The two subjects replaced mathematics and physical sciences and were meant to strengthen the civil technology specializations. However, such a move looked

miscalculated as the content in the specializations was already congested. Moreover, in both newly introduced subjects (technical mathematics and technical sciences), the content was found to be indistinctive from the physical sciences and mathematics (Moloi & Motlhabane, 2023), but a replication.

With proper implementation, technical education subjects such as woodworking, civil services, and construction can help reduce the dependent population (not the working population). Moreover, as articulated by Ohia & Osah (2020), imparting woodworking, civil services, and construction technical skills to learners in Nigeria is important because the rate of youth unemployment is increasing, and this poses a great danger to a nation's social and economic stability.

So, investigating the demise of technical subjects in South Africa is key to providing an insight into key contributory factors to the sluggish economy linked to the high unemployment rate, especially amongst the youth.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Vygotsky's (1978) articulation of activity theory, which holds that the human subject uses tools to achieve an object, anchors this study. In Vygotsky's approach, an object is the motivation for the activity, and the activity is mediated by artifacts. In relation to the Civil Technology specializations, the use of tools to produce artifacts is critical for learners in schools for practical activities. This can only be realistic if learners follow pre-service teachers' instructions to manipulate tools and equipment, which are central to teaching pedagogies. When this occurs, learners will learn by doing, which equates to acclimating to the world of work. However, Bhebhe and Maila (2016) caution that the few periods for practical subjects in schools mean that the DBE does not take practical subjects as important.

To complete the PATs successfully for developing hands-on practical skills in the construction, civil services, and woodworking specializations, learners will need more time in the workshops. In support, Moloi & Motlhabane (2023) point out that the practical nature of any technology education subject makes it unique in content and approach.

Imparting technical skills through upgrading skills training for learners in Nigeria has been given as a way of enhancing employability and promoting self-employment (Inyiagu, 2014). From this discussion, to transfer practical hands-on skills to learners, it could be reasoned that civil technology teaching pedagogies should be rooted in the practical aspect of the subject. As such, Vilaythong (2011) points out that such pedagogies should involve the acquisition of practical activities designed to give learners, at some point, the opportunity to observe and manipulate real objects and materials. Consistent manipulation of real objects will build learners confidence in acquiring the requisite real-world, hands-on skills. Consequently, the partnership with industries could give learners opportunities to manipulate equipment under supervision. Exposure to real-world equipment usage could equip learners with practical skills. Chakamba et al. (2013) postulate that skill development increases creativity and employability for self-reliance.

From the above views, it is worth noting that when learners are familiar with using equipment and material, they can use that in trades like making wooden objects, building brick walls, plastering, and plumbing, for example, to earn a living. This hands-on approach, according to Gwembire & Katsaruware (2013), would then enable learners to lead a productive life after school. So, in the

subjects under investigation, it appears that learners need more hands-on training as opposed to receiving more theory (Green et al., 2017). Therefore, Vygotsky's activity theory becomes relevant and is considered a strong instrument. The theory is bringing about positive modifications in academic education to allow learners to apply what they have learned to the real world (Guo et al., 2016). In other words, the theory calls for authentic learning which require activities to be designed to give learners "real-world" experiences to solve real world problems. Learning of this kind helps learners to use classroom learning to acquire hands-on skills whereby they could themselves be labor employers rather than seeking low-paid jobs (Kola & Kehinde, 2019).

This shows that it is only through learning by doing that learners can be acquainted with the desired technical skills for self-reliance. The researcher has years of personal experience teaching civil technology subjects at a secondary school and pre-service teachers at higher education institutions (HEIs) and has observed that schools do not invest in civil technology-specialized subjects. Of greater concern is that some schools do not even have a timetable for practical work.

According to Mhlongo et al. (2023), schools continue to severely neglect practical work due to a lack of resources. In addition, Mokhothu (2020) posited that although practical work is extremely important in all technology education subjects, most schools in South Africa are under resourced and have been neglecting practical work due to a lack of resources. Under the circumstances, the interest of this study was to establish how skills development in the specializations, as posited by Vygotsky's activity theory, is being handled by schools using the Civil Technology specializations as the barometer.

The use of activity theory as a theoretical framework has allowed the researcher to specifically focus on questions pertaining to the handling of technical subjects, which can be somewhat referred to as their demise, linking to the worsening unemployment rate in the country. In this study, the availability and manipulation of tools and equipment by learners in civil services, construction, and woodworking and the way learners should develop hands-on technical skills were conceptualized as ideal for skill development for learners to sustain themselves economically.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a mixed-methods approach to investigate the demise of technical subjects and the impact that has on the stagnating economy of the country. Mixed methods research design involve the use of both qualitative and quantitative research approaches in one study. Mixed methods research may be the correct choice when the research process specifies that quantitative or qualitative data alone cannot sufficiently answer the research question (Sharma et al., 2023). From this perspective, this study was piloted to assess its feasibility, as mixed methods gathering data can be challenging if it lacks relevance (Ganesha & Aithal, 2022). According to Simon (2011), a pilot study may address several logistical issues in that regard. As part of a research strategy, Simon (2011) established that the following factors can be resolved prior to the study:

1. Check that the instructions are comprehensible
2. Check the wording of the survey
3. Check the validity and reliability of results
4. Check that the statistical and analytical process are efficient

This study ran a pilot study to satisfy the above factors and measure whether the study was feasible. We carried out this preliminary work before the actual study.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is the overall strategy that researchers use to investigate different components of a study in a coherent and logical way. Before beginning the research process, researchers should understand the nature of the research needed and how this determines the whole research process. This included framing research questions, deciding on the nature of the data to collect, ways to analyze the data, and finally how to report it. A research design, therefore, outlines how the whole investigation is carried out.

Mixed-methods research, according to Mwita (2022), goes beyond a mere superficial combination of quantitative and qualitative data. Similarly, Mwita (2022) affirms that quantitative and qualitative methods may be combined to build, confirm, and improve theory.

The combination of qualitative and quantitative methods is often used by researchers to enhance and validate research inquiries. To heighten the dependability and trustworthiness of the data and their interpretation, this study used statistical methods to establish validity and reliability for the quantitative method. The questions in the questionnaire were drawn up based on the literature review. Cronbach's Alpha was used to measure reliability to understand whether the questions in the questionnaire reliably measure the same underlying variables. For qualitative validity and reliability, the study employed methods which are reliable and trustworthy. In this case, interview questions were piloted with different samples of pre-service students. The purpose was to make sure that everyone in the sample not only understands the questions but understands them in the same way (Hazzi & Maldaon, 2015). This study, accordingly, used mixed approaches to corroborate the findings from different research components. As a result, a survey in the form of questionnaires was administered along with semi-structured interviews to get in-depth information from 3rd year pre-service students' teachers on the state of technical subjects offered in South African schools. As advised, the study was only limited to Civil Technology's woodworking, civil services, and construction specializations. The questionnaire contained Linkert scale-type items with several options. Quantitative data were presented and analyzed statistically to give a frequency distribution.

POPULATION AND SAMPLING

A population consists of all the objects or events of a certain type about which researchers seek information (Chadwick, 2017). According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2011), sampling is to obtain data from a smaller group or subset of the total population in such a way that the knowledge gained is representative of the total population under study. As a result, the group of pre-service students' teachers was conveniently chosen from four higher education institutions (HEIs) offering civil technology teacher training in the four provinces of the Republic of South Africa. This convenient sampling technique was chosen in order to focus on the characteristic population that was of interest. Battaglia (2011) describes purposive sampling as a non-probability sampling method aiming to produce a sample that can be considered "representative" of the population. This study was focused on Civil Technology teacher training in South African HEIs and therefore, by purposive or judgmental sampling, only Civil Technology teacher Training Institutions in South Africa were selected. It is worth noting that out of the twenty-six public HEIs across nine

provinces in South Africa, only five offer civil technology teacher training. At first, the study aimed to use all five HEIs with 83 pre-service teachers in total, but the fifth HEI was left out due to logistical reasons. That reduced the number of respondents from 89 to 79. Due to constraints beyond the researcher's control, the study couldn't include other technology specialisations such as mechanical and electrical technologies but focused only on the civil technology specialisations from four HEIs in the four provinces, as follows:

Table 1. Population of the study

HEI	PROVINCE
A	Free State
B	Eastern Cape
C	Gauteng
D	KwaZulu Natal

From the above population, seventy-nine 3rd year pre-service students' teachers studying civil technology were conveniently chosen as respondents. These are student teachers who have been to many schools across the country for work-integrated learning (WIL) in the form of teaching practice. Because these respondents have been to schools in various provinces, they have experienced how the civil technology specializations are handled. It should be noted that, though pre-service students' teachers' study in the HEIs from the four provinces, they are allowed to conduct their WIL in any school anywhere in the country. Maeko and Makgato (2017) note that for the credibility of samples, there should be accuracy that mirrors the target population. Consequently, the selected sample was relevant. It was chosen carefully to provide accurate information as the students are in their final year studying for civil technology teacher qualification.

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

Data gathering tools are fact-finding strategies to collect data. Mwita (2022) advises that data collection methods are means, tools, or techniques that researchers use to collect data for their respective projects. These methods and instruments are not specific to any one question; instead, they provide data to address research questions.

This way, data from different sources may be triangulated to allow for more accurate research findings. In this study, both questionnaires and interviews were developed to collect quantitative and qualitative data, respectively, concerning the views of 79 3rd year Civil Technology pre-service student teachers.

Because of the larger numbers, focus group interviews were used. The respondents were clustered into 6–7 groups per group to form 10 groups (A–J), and the interviews did not take more than 10 minutes per group. It should be mentioned that pre-service students' teachers focus group interviews were used to get clarity as a follow-up to some of the critical answers given in the questionnaire. The interviews were first transcribed and then recurring themes extracted. Each

transcription was considered with the aim of identifying key issues. Descriptions were then formulated from the key issues identified as relevant to the study, and these were coded. Themes, which are a pattern of answers emerging consistently and more often and so as highlight a common issue, were created and then categorized into headings and constructively narrated with the support of verbatim. The quantitative data were presented and analyzed statistically and responses represented as percentages. The data from completed survey questionnaires were also coded and captured in SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 23 for Windows.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

QUESTIONNAIRE DATA PRESENTATION

The following table shows the distribution of percentages because of agreeing, disagreeing, and somewhat agreeing and disagreeing. This was to test practices encountered by pre-service teachers regarding the teaching and learning of the Civil Technology Specialisations practical aspect.

Table 2: Pre-Service teachers' responses on the Civil Technology specializations

Statement/Indicators	% Distribution				
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Somewhat agree nor disagree
1. Have learners completed Practical Assessment Tasks from Grade 10?	14.3	18.3	36.8	30.6	0
2. Do schools have qualified teachers in the specializations?	8.8	8.8	54.4	26.3	1.7
3. There is enough material for practical	7	24.6	38.6	24.6	5.2
4. Learners get the opportunity to interact with theory and practical	10.5	15.8	49.1	24.6	0
5. There is adequate supply of basic hand tools for practical'	7	15.8	59.6	15.8	0
6. There is enough time set aside for practical	16.1	29.8	29.8	24.3	0
7. All Civil Technology specializations are theoretical'	57.9	29.8	1.8	10.5	0
8. Schools have no capacity to handle practical	54.4	26.3	14.0	5.3	0

Table 2 above shows percentages from Questions 1 to 8. The table reveals the most and least frequent responses. The most frequent student responses are shown by Q7, which used the statement 'all civil technology specializations are theoretical' with a staggering 87.7% of pre-service students' teachers disagreeing with the statement. This could be because learners are not exposed to practical work often enough because of time constraints and the unavailability of resources. The finding ties in with pre-service teachers' responses to Q6, where some of the schools are set to have no time set aside for practical. The second-most common pre-service students' teacher's responses were for Q2 and Q8 at 80.7% each. These findings are a direct indictment on

the schools and the DBE. By employing unqualified teachers, both the schools and the department show a level of ignorance about the need for hands-on skill development. This corroborates the assertion from Magolego et al. (2023) that some teachers focus on the theoretical part of the subjects because they lack the skills and resources to facilitate practical lessons. In the same vein, Mhlongo et al. (2023) add that practical work is highly neglected in schools. Next were Q4 and Q5, at 73.7% and 75.5% each, where pre-service students' teachers also respectively disagreed with statements "learners get the opportunity to interact with theory and practical" and "there is adequate supply of basic hand tools for practical". These are unfortunate findings because they mean most learners have no opportunity to interact with tools. The implications are that learners will graduate from school with no skills to make ends meet if they are unwilling to further their studies. In contradiction, learners from the old system were well skilled for self-sustenance (Maeko & Makgato, 2014), which reveals the failures of the current system.

Q 1 and 3 reflected on the need for material to complete the PATs. In response, pre-service teachers again disagreed at 67.4% and 63.2% that there is enough material for the PATs. Without material, the subjects remain theoretical, which flies in the face of skill development.

The above responses indicate a perceived lack of confidence for schools to develop learners' practical hands-on skills in the specializations. These responses tie in with Mokhothu (2020), who asserted that although practical work is extremely important in all technology education subjects, most of the schools in South Africa are under-resourced and have been neglecting practical work. In support, Green et al. (2017) argues that for learners to acquire such skills, they would likely need more hands-on training as opposed to the awkward reality where they generally just receive theoretical education.

INTERVIEWS DATA PRESENTATION

In response to the research questions, the following table shows the interview schedule used to obtain data from respondents.

Table 3. Pre-Service teachers' responses on the Civil Technology specializations

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1. Are learners completing their PATs from Grade 10?
 2. Will matric graduates from the specializations prepared to enter job market
 3. Do schools possess enough tools and materials for practical?
-

Responding to Q1 from Table 3, which was structured to source views on whether "learners complete the PATs from Grade 10".

THEME: SKILLS DEVELOPMENT FOR LEARNERS FROM GRADE 10

Coincidentally, almost all the pre-service students' teachers responded by saying learners do not really complete the PATs from Grade 10. Without such a process, there is just no way learners will develop skills within a short space of time in Grade 12. That corroborates the views expressed in the questionnaire. The pre-service students' teachers went further to allege that it is only in Grade 12 that learners do practical to cover for 25%, which contributes to the learner's final mark. One pre-service student teacher remarked, "Schools do not invest in practical technology education, and as a result, what schools are doing is a disgrace to skills development". These developments

resonate well with the assertion of Nani (2014) that teaching practical subjects in schools needs more time to produce individuals who can create jobs for themselves.

Question 2 was about whether “matriculation graduates from the specializations will be ready to enter the job market”.

THEME: JOB-MARKET OPPORTUNITIES

Pre-service teachers' responses on this question clearly indicates their low confidence level on the preparation of learners. One student from group C said, “I don't see how the underprepared learners will enter the relevant technical job market without further development”. Another student from group E said that “with a lot of theory to cover for each term, there's just no time for practical as learners have to write examinations at the end of the year. The introduction of technical mathematics and technical sciences was another blunder by the Department”. These responses further expose the DBE-led schooling system's failure to invest in the development of technical skills within their specializations. The responses find support in Bhebhe & Maila (2016), who cautioned that limited training and few periods for civil technology practical work reveal that DBE does not take practical subjects as important. Unfortunately, the findings contradict those of Maeko & Makgato (2014), who found that some of the learners who went through technical school during the apartheid era were either self-employed or employed without any further training.

Responding to Q3 which asked if “schools possess enough tools and material for practical”. The following theme emerged from the respondents:

THEME: EQUIPMENT FOR PRACTICAL

Again, these responses show the dire situation for skill development in schools. One respondent from group J painted a bleak future for construction, civil services, and woodworking specializations by saying, “The specializations aren't taking preference in schools, authentic learning is central to skills development, and it doesn't look like school principals understand the impact”. Another respondent from group H echoed the same sentiments by saying, “Until the government and the school principals understand how critical these specializations are, we are going nowhere as a country, and the youth coming out of the system will continue adding to the unemployment numbers”.

These unfortunate responses find support in Msibi (2021), who contended that the quality of skills training offered by technical schools is falling short of the required levels with little alignment to the needs of the labor market.

Vygotsky's activity theory (1978) outlines that activities that learners engage in lead to better acquisition of hands-on skills. It is contended that such could only be possible with the availability of equipment, tools, and materials for learners to manipulate. Practical work, which needs time to perform, defines the unique nature of the specializations. However, it is worrying to see schools buying materials for Grade 12's to engage in activities for the purpose of completing the PATs for marks only.

IMPLICATIONS FOR FINDINGS

This paper was an attempt to understand the relationship between the skyrocketing unemployment rate and a lack of technical skill development in South Africa. In other words, the study creates a platform for the need for various stakeholders to have conversations about how schools and the Department of Basic Education are handling subjects meant for technical skills development. Additionally, the study can contribute to the need for supervision in these subjects, which are critical for sustenance and job creation. In relation to Vygotsky's activity theory which underpinned this study, the teaching and learning pedagogies for all technical education subjects should be centered around hands-on activities.

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to evaluate the demise of technical subjects in South Africa, focusing on Civil Technology's Civil Services, Construction, and Woodworking specializations. The study was motivated by the skyrocketing unemployment rate among youth. Unfortunately, the study found that both technical schools and the Department of Basic Education are responsible for the dire state of the subjects. In addition to hiring unqualified teachers for specializations, the lack of basic tools and materials in schools is a startling revelation. The findings revealed the shocking state of technical subjects owing to the authorities' failure to implement the curriculum correctly. With a battered South African economy that is unable to create jobs, South Africa currently needs skilled youth for self-reliance, and that is only possible if the government starts investing heavily in the development of technical skills.

As attested by Vygotsky, technical hands-on skills can be best developed through activities and that is only possible through the interaction with tools and equipment, which is unfortunately not the case. In support of the theory, the study revealed hands-on learning skills as a panacea for addressing the skyrocketing unemployment rate in the country. In fact, the study considers authentic learning as central to exposing learners to hands-on skills in technical education. Skills development takes time, which schools don't have, as the Department of Basic Education added yet other theoretical subjects in the form of technical mathematics and technical sciences, which proved to add no value. Such actions point to the extent of confusion that the department has with their misunderstanding of the specializations. Unfortunately, this has robbed many youths' lifelong skills. More worrying and concerning, the schools do not seem to be really interested in this critical part of the trade's education trajectory.

In complicity, the Department of Basic Education, as the custodians of the education system, has become equally involved in this deceitful act to help schools churn out learners from the specializations who are only armed with theory without technical hands-on skills. This situation makes mockery of the curriculum policy which is explicit about the skills which learners should possess upon leaving schools. Sadly, this has left learners with no hope for employment or self-sustenance after their schooling years. Such irresponsible actions could potentially contribute to the country's rapidly rising unemployment rate. Since Vygotsky asserts that hands-on activities are the best practice for skill development, it is sad that learners spent time on theoretical aspects in Grade 10, which the study exposed as a contributing factor to the demise of technical subjects. This study contributed immensely to the body of knowledge about the need for intentional pedagogies for hands-on skill development in technology education. Despite the notable

contribution to the technical field, it is important to highlight that the study has some limitations that can be addressed in follow-up studies in the area. Firstly, this study had a limited number of participants, making it difficult for the findings to be generalized to all technology education specialization areas in South Africa. Secondly, this study only focused on student teachers from the Civil Technology specialization area; student teachers in other specializations may have different views on the nature of specializations to nurture learners' hands-on practical skills.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommends that the Department of Basic Education as the custodians of education in the South African schools should intervene by making skills hands-on skills acquisition in Civil Technology Specialisations a reality. This can be done by ensuring that schools that offer the specialisations do comply with the minimum curriculum policy which has clearly set out the criteria which schools should consider for offering the specialisations effectively. Moreover, the Department should put mechanisms in place to ensure that schools do employ qualified teaching staff and are consistently supplied with material and equipment. The supply of equipment to schools should be coupled with a comprehensive plan on how routine maintenance of the equipment will be handled. It is further recommended for the Department of Basic Education to establish a team of experts to evaluate the usefulness of the recently introduced Technical Sciences and Technical Mathematics. Moreover, teachers are advised to improvise by infusing simulation activities in their pedagogies when no materials and equipment are available. Lastly, the study calls for collaboration between business and the Department of Basic Education to revitalise the technical education field in schools. Such cooperation should also allow for learners to visit industry for exposure to hand-on experience.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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